

WebAssembly in Building Internet of Things Systems

Systematic Literature Review of Use Cases, Characteristics,
Opportunities, and Threats

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WebAssembly in Building Internet of Things Systems.

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WebAssembly in Building Internet of Things Systems. Systematic Literature Review of Use Cases, Characteristics, Opportunities, and Threats.

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This thesis explores the potential of WebAssembly (Wasm) in the Internet of Things (IoT) domain, particularly in the contexts of resource-constrained device usage and cloud/edge computing. A state-of-the-art review is conducted to understand the potential applications of Wasm in improving or innovating existing IoT systems, software development practices, and system architectures. Findings illustrate diverse applications of Wasm in building IoT systems, including efficient implementation of cloud and edge computing services and enabling efficient code execution on resource-constrained devices. Despite the challenges of potential performance loss and complexities of deploying Wasm modules, it is positioned as a promising technology for IoT, with its lightweight design, flexible interfacing, and energy efficiency. The study illustrates the potential of Wasm in shaping IoT systems through its interoperability, reduced latency, and simplified deployment process. This research paves the way for future exploration and application of Wasm in the IoT landscape.

Keywords WebAssembly, Wasm, Internet of Things, IoT**urn** <https://aaltodoc.aalto.fi>

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1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) became a widely used concept that describes modern systems across various industries. According to Nikolaos Goumagias et al. review [1], the term describes an ecosystem of connected devices that can collect internal and external data from objects or subjects that the devices are attached to. The system is capable of analyzing, transmitting, and acting based on the analysis according to goals and certain limitations, such as resource availability, privacy, and security issues. These IoT ecosystems are integrated with cloud computing to alleviate the complexity of service delivery, networking, data processing, and management, where the necessity of fog or edge computing is notable [2].

Edge computing describes the processing and analysis of data at a network edge close to the data source with the aim of reducing any communication latency, for example, between data-generating IoT devices and actuators. Applications and services involved in such a system often run on different hardware architectures, communicate via various protocols, and depend on a unique set of libraries; thus, they are described as heterogeneous systems and system-of-systems.

Massimo Villari et al. introduce Osmotic Computing [3] as a concept of Cloud and Edge integration with the Internet of Things where many research challenges were introduced, such as in microservice management and networking, efficient offloading of computation, and security of integrating between different datacenters and edge devices. This article also describes virtualization technologies as a breakthrough technology that tackles the complexity of running applications in heterogeneous and evolving environments.

Virtualization technologies add an abstraction layer above complex systems, such as hardware or an operating system, and emulate their behavior. In addition to hypervisor-based virtual machines and container-based

systems like LXC, the consequent emergence of Docker and Kubernetes created a wave of transformation in how modern applications are deployed and managed in the cloud [4].

Recently, the web ecosystem adopted WebAssembly (Wasm) binary instruction format for a stack-based virtual machine and WebAssembly System Interface (WASI). Wasm/WASI currently is a compilation target for multiple programming languages and can be executed by runtimes with different implementations. The performance of runtimes and lightweight modular nature of Wasm attracted the attention of researchers to analyze the capabilities and opportunities of running Wasm for cloud and edge computing. For example, one study [5] provides evidence that running Wasm outperforms Docker in cold-start times and memory consumption. Therefore, it is relevant to continue research on the possible integration of Wasm with existing technologies and the benefits that it can bring to the ecosystem.

The aim of this thesis is to determine the potential of applying Wasm in the Internet of Things within the context of virtualization and cloud/edge computing by conducting a state-of-the-art review. This is supported by answering relevant research questions and synthesizing the results and observations with the broader context of IoT and software development.

The thesis first covers a relevant background in Chapter 2 to assist in understanding the discussed concepts and establish a context for the literature review. Then Chapter 3 covers the literature review process in great detail. Chapter 4 provides extracted information results from the selected literature for answering supporting research questions. And finally, Chapter 5 answers the main research question that aligns with the primary goal of this thesis. All the results and observations of the literature review are concluded in Chapter 6.

2. Background

This chapter covers the relevant background information that assists in understanding the concepts covered in this thesis and establishes a context for the literature review.

2.1 Internet of Things

The term Internet of Things (IoT) has been used for about two decades and has undergone several transformations. The first devices connected to the internet with machine-to-machine (M2M) communication capabilities started appearing in the 1980s when students at Carnegie Mellon University connected the department vending machine to their local network [6]. However, the concept of IoT was not widely adopted until the 2000s, when advancements in wireless technology and the proliferation of smartphones led to an increased number of devices connected to the internet.

IoT adoption is growing across multiple industries with a vast range of applications. The applications are broadly addressed in [7] and include healthcare, transportation, agriculture, and smart homes. The research on applications is also conducted for each sector specifically. For example, the survey of IoT technologies in healthcare [8] demonstrates that a system of sensors enables the collection of vital health information from patients for remote autonomous monitoring and diagnosis. The research also shows that the IoT-based system can be integrated with other emerging technologies in machine learning, fog/edge computing, blockchain, and wearable devices. Similarly, in agriculture, IoT enables extensive automation in crops, livestock, and environmental monitoring, harvesting, as well as smart water management, disease management, and supply chain management [9].

As evident, the process of designing and building IoT systems relies heav-

ily on the latest technological developments. The IoT-enabling technologies are described through common IoT architecture layers¹ [7], [10]:

- **The perception layer** identifies and tracks objects, collects data through sensors, and interacts with environments.
- **The network layer** connects the devices, including servers, through an integrated network and transmits information from origins to a target destination.
- **The service layer** (also known as the middleware layer) stores and processes data received from the network layer as a set of integrated services.
- **The application layer** provides services to the end-user in the context of a specific application, for example, smart homes, smart cities, and smart transportation.

The perception layer involves sensor and sensor management technologies, namely RFID (Radio Frequency Identification), medical, neural, environmental, and chemical sensors, as well as actuators that react to input data [7]. The network layer relies on an IoT network protocol stack that may include IEEE 802.15.4, 6LoWPAN, Zigbee, Z-Wave, MQTT, and CoAP [10]. Additionally, [7] covers Bluetooth Low Energy, Narrowband IoT, Sigfox, Weightless, Neul, LoRaWAN, and LWM2M. Most of them are designed to allow low-powered devices to communicate specific types of information within specific contexts more efficiently.

Considering the heterogeneity of both network protocols and hardware architectures, the necessity of a service layer that incorporates middleware between the network and application layers is more apparent. The middleware layer addresses challenges of interoperability, abstraction, scalability, big data analytics, security and privacy, and cloud infrastructure integration [7]. Middleware could be classified into multiple categories based on its purpose and architecture: event-based, service-oriented, database-oriented, semantic, and application-specific [7]. Jie Lin et al. [10] provide

¹The provided layers do not completely represent IoT systems and would differ from case to case based on a specific system implementation. For instance, while [10] considers the service layer in their analysis, [7] adds a pre-processing layer before networking with an emphasis on the implementation of smart gateways.

some alternative classifications and suggest that the service layer must also include interface definitions, service management, resource management, and resource sharing capabilities.

The IoT services are integrated into the cloud to leverage its scalability, adaptability, and data handling capabilities [2], [7], [10]. However, cloud computing is not capable of addressing IoT requirements of mobility, real-time low-latency communication, and power constraints [7]. To fulfill such requirements, fog/edge computing extends cloud computing to bring the computation to the edge of a network closer to the things [2], [7], [10].

When designing and building such distributed systems, the aim of better mobility and decreased latency could be considered a cost-minimizing effort. For an efficient IoT edge computing system, Lin et al. [10] emphasize the importance of resource allocation across edge nodes and devices, i.e., create a system for effectively sharing computation across servers and devices to minimize the overall cost of running the system.

2.2 WebAssembly

WebAssembly (Wasm) is a low-level binary format resembling assembly that defines a virtual instruction set architecture based on a stack machine [11]. It is an open standard developed and maintained by World Wide Web Consortium and initially designed for browsers to execute close-to-native code alongside JavaScript. However, Wasm modules are not restricted to be executed inside web browsers. The core specification only concerns the ISA, which is designed to be supported by as many existing hardware architectures by making assumptions that are broadly supported across modern hardware. As a result of this design, Wasm is mostly language, platform, and hardware independent, as long as there is a Wasm runtime embedded into the system where the Wasm module can be executed.

The work on WebAssembly specification was publicly announced on the 17th of June, 2015 [12]. Previous work concerning similar design goals was asm.js from Mozilla and Google Portable Native Client. Instead of building incompatible tool sets for achieving similar goals, representatives from Google, Mozilla, Microsoft, and other key organizations established the working group and initiated the project. Considering this, WebAssembly is expected to be neutral and interoperable to be supported by all major browsers. So far, browsers like Mozilla Firefox, Chrome, and Safari support

Wasm and most of the proposed features [13].

Execution of WebAssembly is based around modules which are units for loading, compiling, and deploying the Wasm bytecode [14]. The module contains information about types, functions, tables, memories, and globals. Most essentially, modules define imports and exports, which can be used for initializing the module. Host runtime can use this import and export mechanism for initializing the Wasm module, link it with other modules at compile-time or run-time, and generally interface with the Wasm module for passing data in both directions. As a simple example, Wasm can export a function named “run“ which would be an entry point that can be called by the host runtime.

At the moment, Wasm relies on a single linear memory provided for it by the host runtime [15]. Combined with the reliance on import and export mechanisms, and structured control flow, WebAssembly provides an opportunity to design a sandbox environment for executing untrusted code from the web. However, it does not mean Wasm prevents all kinds of attacks and still relies on memory-safe code and robust compilation mechanisms to mitigate certain security risks [16].

The process of decoding and validating Wasm can be accomplished regardless of whether the code is run by just-in-time (JIT) compilation, ahead-of-time (AOT) compilation, or by an interpreter.

- Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation involves converting the source code into machine-level instructions during program execution, effectively “just in time“ for use. This approach allows for optimizations that can consider the actual runtime conditions, often resulting in highly efficient execution.
- Ahead-Of-Time (AOT) compilation transforms the source code into machine code before running the program. While it may not have as many opportunities for runtime optimization as JIT, AOT compilation can result in faster startup times since the code is already compiled at program launch.
- Interpreter reads and executes the code directly, statement by statement. This allows for maximum flexibility, as the code can be altered and rerun immediately without requiring recompilation. However, the execution speed is generally slower than JIT or AOT compilation

The current Wasm ecosystem consists of several runtimes that operate outside the browser, such as Wasmtime, Wamr, Wasmer, Wasm3, and many more. Since executing the Wasm module requires defining an interface, runtimes that do not support a standardized interface would rely on different interface definitions making Wasm modules incompatible across various runtimes. Initially, compilation tools like Emscripten, designed for running C/C++ libraries and apps via Wasm inside the browser, defined an interface that also relies on generating JavaScript code to integrate with the browser effectively.

However, the Emscripten-based interface was not ideal for running Wasm outside the browser. Thus WebAssembly System Interface was introduced as a new standard for implementing an interface for a POSIX-like system calls [17]. This standard allows the gradual implementation of interfaces for accessing hardware resources from Wasm while also enabling a capability-based security model. With the capability-based security model, a Wasm module cannot utilize the available system calls unless explicitly allowed by a host runtime.

WebAssembly is still in active development and does not provide features that would be available when using other programming language runtimes and compilation toolchains. WebAssembly feature proposals such as exception handling, garbage collection, and threads are not yet widely adopted and standardized [13]. Regarding WASI, many of the interfaces are not yet clearly defined; for instance, interface proposals for Sockets, HTTP, and SQL are in the earliest stage [18].

3. Literature Review

This chapter covers the literature review process. The methodology section outlines the research questions and steps taken to perform the literature selection and review. The next section gives an overview of the selected articles and their contents in relation to the research questions. Then the last section describes how research questions are answered given the selected literature and their characteristics.

3.1 Methodology

The literature review follows a systematic literature review process as outlined by Kitchenham et al. [19]. The review is conducted to answer the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** How is WebAssembly applied in building Internet of Things systems?
- **RQ2:** What are the advantages and disadvantages of WebAssembly when building Internet of Things systems?
- **RQ3:** What are the opportunities and threats of using WebAssembly when designing Internet of Things systems?

At first, preliminary searches were conducted to identify the scope of the research. A simple search of “WebAssembly” in the ACM Digital Library presented 281 results. One source [5] provided a clue that the benefits of WebAssembly could apply to edge computing and the Internet of Things. A consequent search of “WebAssembly AND (‘Internet of Things’ OR IoT)” decreased the number of results to 76, and adding “Edge OR Cloud” to the

search query marginally decreased it further to 64, which signifies that cloud or edge computing is discussed within the context of IoT in most of the cases. Considering the familiarity with Wasm3 runtime that can run on resource-constrained devices, the former search of “WebAssembly AND (‘Internet of Things’ OR IoT)“ was finally chosen for the literature review to avoid the exclusion of potential use cases of WebAssembly outside of edge or cloud computing.

The search was conducted on the ACM Digital Library and IEEE Xplore between 10 March and 15 March 2023. The search query included all metadata, while the results were filtered to include everything published before 2023 to narrowly limit the scope and make it more reproducible. The search yielded 67 results in ACM Digital Library and 16 in IEEE Xplore.

The sources went through two inclusion/exclusion rounds. The first inclusion process is described in Table 3.1. It resulted in 39 articles that excluded more than half of the ACM Digital Library results since articles discuss other computer science topics.

Table 3.1. First literature inclusion process

Step	Inclusion criteria
1	Must be conference or journal articles
2	Must not be duplicates
3	Abstract must indicate WebAssembly usage or discussion
Resulting articles: 39	
ACM Digital Library: $\approx 34\%$ retained	
IEEE Xplore: 100% retained	

Table 3.2. Categorization of WebAssembly use case environments in IoT

Environment	Category
Internet of Things layers	Perception layer
	Network layer
	Service layer
Computing environments	Cloud and edge computing

Some articles within the resulting articles were primarily about Wasm but mentioned IoT without significance and did not answer the research questions. Therefore, the second inclusion process described in Table 3.3 is based on the categorization outlined in Table 3.2 that stems from the IoT

background information in Section 2.1.

Table 3.3. Second literature inclusion process based on categorization

Step	Inclusion criteria
1	Wasm environment of usage or discussion must fit into one of the categories outlined in Table 3.2
Resulting articles: 27	
ACM Digital Library: $\approx 57\%$ retained	
IEEE Xplore: $\approx 87\%$ retained	

Abstracts must indicate that Wasm is used for the perception, network, or service layer of IoT, otherwise for cloud or edge computing. In cases where it needed to be clarified, some articles were skimmed to verify the application of Wasm in IoT or cloud and edge computing. The final number of articles included in the literature review is 27. Still, most of the IEEE Xplore articles were included since it is unlikely to discuss WebAssembly as a computer science topic in an electrical engineering journal.

Figure 3.1. Literature review process diagram

Although the final set of selected articles is categorized by use case environment, it is not sufficient for answering the research questions. Therefore, articles are examined and categorized further to establish their general overview. The overview is then used as an additional context when answering the research questions.

3.2 Overview of Literature

The number of articles by publication year shows an increasing trend indicating a growing relevance of the research area.

Figure 3.2. Number of articles by publication year.

After the categorization based on Table 3.2, perception layer usage and cloud/edge usage emerged as the primary categories for differentiating between articles. Out of 27 articles, 11 discuss Wasm usage in the IoT perception layer, 12 discuss Wasm usage in cloud/edge computing, and 4 discuss both device and cloud usage. IEEE Xplore yielded more articles that discuss device usage, while ACM Digital Library yielded more articles that discuss cloud/edge usage.

Figure 3.3. Comparison of articles published in ACM Digital Library and IEEE Xplore databases categorized by Wasm usage environment

Categorization into network and service layers did not provide significant information. All articles categorized into service layer usage were under the cloud/edge category. However, the distinction between the two categories was unclear. The network layer was discussed only in two articles in the context of cloud and device integration.

The type of research may also influence how Wasm usage is perceived. Therefore, three main types were derived based on the contents of the articles:

- **Report:** Research paper primarily describes a new system using Wasm developed by the authors, including some reviews and benchmarking.
- **Review:** Research paper that primarily reviews technologies that are not built by the authors and provides an outlook of Wasm usage and its potential. It may include benchmarks.
- **Benchmark:** Research paper evaluating technologies that are not developed by the authors primarily using benchmarking techniques.

The selected papers consist of **18 report, 6 review, and 3 benchmark** articles.

3.3 Answering Research Questions

The **RQ1** was answered by carefully reading the articles to derive the specific use cases of Wasm for building IoT or IoT-related systems. Key insights from each article were extracted and summarized, forming a comprehensive list of seven major use cases where Wasm is being utilized. The summary of each use case was also supplemented with references to the respective articles from which the information was derived, providing a rich and robust answer to the research question. Moreover, additional insights from benchmark articles and review articles that did not fit into a specific use case were also mentioned to provide a holistic understanding of the topic.

However, when attempting to answer **RQ2**, certain characteristics of WebAssembly were more emphasized based on the multifaceted context under which the WebAssembly features are utilized or discussed. Alongside varying use cases and research methodology, papers presented WebAssembly at different abstraction levels, from reporting on custom compilers and runtimes to a high-level overview of complex orchestration systems. In order to establish relationships between these characteristics, the **RQ2** was answered by extracting use-case-specific higher-level observations organized under corresponding subsections. The characteristics were also

supplemented with references to the respective articles.

The **RQ3** about opportunities and threats of utilizing Wasm requires relating the ideas extracted from the articles to a broader context of IoT and software development. It also corresponds with the primary goal of this thesis to provide a high-level overview regarding the potential of applying Wasm in building IoT systems. The RQ3 was answered by organizing the main discussion points under the broad contexts of IoT.

- RQ1 is answered under Section 4.1.
- RQ1 is answered under Section 4.2.
- RQ1 is answered under Section 5.1 and 5.2.

4. Results

This chapter covers the information relevant to answering RQ1 and RQ2 extracted from the selected literature. The first section lists Wasm use cases and answers RQ1. The second section reports on the characteristics of Wasm and answers RQ2.

4.1 WebAssembly Use Cases

The following list compiles all the derived use cases of Wasm for building IoT or IoT-related systems and consequently answers RQ1.

1. **Function-as-a-service (FaaS) platform.** When Wasm is discussed within the cloud/edge computing context, the dominant use case of Wasm is in building FaaS platforms. Hall and Ramachandran [20] implemented their FaaS prototype in 2019 using NodeJS and V8 Wasm runtime and called for a custom runtime for future work. Gadepalli et al. [21] explored the opportunities of Wasm for serverless computing. Then, in 2020, the same research group built a custom runtime system from scratch designed for FaaS [22]. Related group expanded on the research by applying the FaaS platform for executing function DAGs (directed acyclic graphs) [23]. Gackstatter et al. [24] took a different approach to Hall and Ramachandran and integrated Wasm into an existing FaaS platform Apache OpenWhisk instead of building a separate FaaS platform. A review from Kjorveziroski et al. [25] further shows that Wasm can be integrated with Docker and mentions orchestration systems WasmCloud and Spin. Those integrations and systems may bring Wasm beyond FaaS to deploy and manage whole microservices.

2. **Application offloading/migration system.** Another dominant use

case of Wasm in the cloud/edge context is in building application offloading/migration systems. The earliest work among the relevant selected literature used Wasm in offloading web applications from a mobile device to cloud/edge servers using HTML5 web worker [26]. The following research papers referenced this work as a basis or related work. Li et al. built a higher-level runtime called WiProg around Wasmer and Wasm3 open source runtimes and added support for IoT application migration, presenting better performance than the system based on a web worker [27]. Nomad migration system only leveraged the Wasm3 interpreter to effectively pause and resume software execution [28]. A review from the same authors of Nomad [29] explored the opportunities offered by Wasm and proposed several models for building an application migration system based on Wasm.

3. **OS with a built-in universal runtime environment.** Few papers present operating systems with a built-in Wasm runtime in an attempt to allow the running of interoperable software between cloud, edge, and IoT devices. Wasmachine presented in [30] and [31] runs AOT compiled Wasm at an operating system level in order to alleviate the overhead of handling Wasm system calls and make it more performant and accessible for resource-constraint devices. Li et al. [32] present ThingSpire OS, which relies on a Wasm runtime to be a universal runtime for all the applications running on the system. It also focuses on more optimized inter-module communication between other deployed Wasm applications.
4. **On-target IR runtime/compiler toolchain.** Few research papers focus on building a toolchain for compiling and running Wasm on a device which is a task at a lower level than building an OS around it. Li et al. (consisting of WiProg and ThingSpire OS authors from the previous use cases) [33] address the challenge of running AOT compilation on resource-constraint devices via their WAIT runtime that does not rely on LLVM compilation toolchain. Similarly, Fabian Scheidl [34] presents a compilation method for WebAssembly with reduced memory consumption. Coterminal to the use case, Wen et al. (consisting of Wasmachine authors from the previous use case) [35] developed a framework for running Java-integrated native code on Android devices with alternative hardware architectures. It utilizes Wasm as an IR and links the native code, compiled using the same compilation method as in Wasmachine,

with the Java runtime.

5. **Trusted execution environment application runtime.** Menetrey et al. [36] presents how Wasm can be used to run applications in trusted execution environments, specifically for ARM TrustZone, allowing it to have multiple isolated enclaves similar to Intel SGX. The consequent review from the same group [37] states that integration of Wasm with TEEs would offer double-sided sandboxing, then explore the feasibility of using Wasm beyond TEEs for the whole cloud-edge continuum.
6. **Hardware resource access control system.** Liu et al. [38] developed a Wasm runtime Aerogel that extends an open source runtime WAMR and leverages sandboxing capabilities of Wasm to achieve fine-grained access control for hardware resources such as peripherals, memory usage, and energy consumption. According to the benchmarks, runtime system checks did not pose a significant overhead.
7. **Remote device software debugging.** Lauwaerts et al. [39] presents a technique for event-based out-of-place debugging of IoT device software. It is implemented by extending WARDuino virtual machine, which abstracts away microcontroller access for Wasm software. Since the state of the VM can be emulated locally, it is more accessible to capture the running software from the remote device and start a debugging session locally, which reminds of the application migration use case.

The three benchmark articles [40]–[42] were not categorized under a specific Wasm use case for building IoT systems, but they provide a general overview of how Wasm performs in cloud/edge computing or IoT peripheral contexts. Few review articles provide a theoretical overview of how Wasm runtimes could be extended to enable generic goals, such as enabling intra-vehicle computing [43], running Wasm on embedded devices [44], or enhancing the security of software running on IoT devices [45]. Relevant ideas from these sources are instead used to answer other research questions.

4.2 WebAssembly Characteristics

Function-as-a-Service

When building a function-as-a-service platform, the instantiation time of the function execution (also called cold start time) is a primary metric and the main bottleneck in VM- and container-based state-of-the-art FaaS platforms [20], [21], [24], [25]. The three Wasm-based FaaS platforms presented in [20], [22], [24] report significantly lower cold start times leading to a much lower average response latency and higher throughput. They also report that each Wasm-based function is lightweight to store [21], [22] and consumes much less memory to execute [24] while offering strong sandboxing mechanisms [20], [22].

However, all of this research recognizes that the benefits of the cold start time of a Wasm function diminish as the computation becomes more CPU-intensive, where overhead due to the Wasm specification becomes more evident. Another aspect that makes Wasm execution less performant is the execution of I/O-intensive computation [22]. This can be attributed to an overhead of handling the interfacing mechanisms with Wasm. In total, this makes Wasm a less viable option when processing a predictable stream of data from a limited set of clients.

Nonetheless, the Wasm-based platform is still a viable alternative in many cases. One reason is that a single cold start incurs a significant time loss which is hard to compensate. Gackstatter et al. [24] show this through a more detailed benchmark designed to replicate a realistic workload. Functions executed by Docker finish faster than one of their Wasm-based executors only 20% of the time. This is where warm starts are likely to be happening. Besides, another Wasm runtime keeps up with the Docker execution speeds even during warm starts. Similarly, the runtime described in [22] shows improved benchmarks compared to previously existing runtimes making the Wasm-based FaaS a more viable option over time. Moreover, many existing complementary approaches that mitigate the cold start times can also be applied to a Wasm-based FaaS platform [24].

As evident, the capabilities of WebAssembly highly depend on the runtime. As one of the earliest works, Hall et al. [20] implemented some level of resource provisioning for functions but mentioned that future work should utilize a custom runtime to support more advanced FaaS features. Sledge runtime [22] addresses this challenge, thus achieving better performance, scheduling, and resource provisioning. On the other

hand, Gackstatter et al. implementation support WASI while Sledge does not [24]. Kjorveziroski et al. point out that WASI helps to compensate for the lack of features in Wasm [25]. It also adds a capability-based security layer to Wasm-based applications [24].

Application Migration / Offloading

The main characteristic of WebAssembly that makes it a suitable option for application offloading and migration is the ability to run on any hardware with an appropriate runtime. Hoque et al. [29] recognize this benefit, while [27], [28] utilize it for their migration system, pointing out that other systems may not take into account the heterogeneity of edge devices. It is possible to achieve a similar level of portability using other cross-platform languages like Java, C#, and JavaScript. However, running Wasm achieves better benchmark results than C# and Java [27], while [26] also claims that Wasm is more performant than JavaScript, and it does not tie down the system to support only a specific language [28].

Similar to the case of FaaS, application migration systems benefit from the lightweight nature of WebAssembly. Compared to VM- and container-based systems, Wasm-based migration does not require capturing the more complex OS state [26]. Building upon the design of WebAssembly, [27] achieves even better performance and energy efficiency compared to the approach of utilizing Wasm taken in [26]. Hoque et al. [28] also create a lightweight migration system, this time utilizing the ability to run Wasm via an interpreter. After all, it is much simpler to capture the linear memory and dependencies of Wasm defined through the import and export mechanisms.

The import and export mechanisms of Wasm allowed [27] to achieve their design goals, while [26] observes that their Wasm-based system can be adapted to existing applications more easily. Similar to the FaaS case, the ability to integrate with the Wasm-based system through standardized interfaces would also be beneficial. Currently, there is no standardized application migration system built around Wasm [29], and [27], [28] only present early prototypes.

IoT Device Application Runtimes

Since WebAssembly relies on an instruction set targeting a virtual machine instead of emulating a whole operating system, the abstraction layer for interfacing with hardware resources can be implemented and customized almost at any level. Hence it is possible to get lightweight runtimes pre-

sented in the literature that are kilobytes in size [31], [33], [35]. Combined with the design of linear memory and control-flow integrity, Wasm serves as a suitable application sandboxing tool for IoT devices [31], [33]. This ability to run WebAssembly on resource-constrained devices opened up a lot of new use cases for it.

The previous section on Wasm characteristics around FaaS mentioned that I/O-intensive applications incurred slow execution. But Wasm runtime embedded into an OS alleviates the system call overhead [30]. The Kernel-intensive scenarios presented in the literature show that executing AOT compiled Wasm at a kernel level was faster by 7-21% compared to native code targeting Linux user space. Executing Wasm in such a way is justified by the sandbox protection. However, implementing software memory isolation bound-checks that were not part of the benchmarks introduces performance loss and may need further work to make it more performant.

Another Wasm-oriented OS ships with an AOT compiler [32], but an on-target compiler is often ponderous [31], [33]. The alternative compilers that directly treat Wasm as an IR can run on Atmel SAM3X8E [34] or even ATmega128 [33]. Having an on-target compiler avoids the reintroduction of the cross-compilation management problem. Wen et al. [35] describe WebAssembly as a more portable IR than LLVM IR and more simplistic to work with than CISC-based IR like Dalvik.

The lack of features in Wasm or WASI is compensated again by extending the interface with the host runtime. This enabled integration of Wasm with Java on Android devices with system call handling via Lua, [35], as well as creating a Wasm runtime for a trusted execution environment [36] and a framework for device resource access control [38]. In addition to WASI capability-based access control to system calls, [38] shows the feasibility of access control for energy and memory consumption, which might be essential for deploying software on resource-constrained devices. Adjacent to this, studies indicate that running WebAssembly is more energy efficient than running tasks in Docker [42] or using JavaScript [41].

5. Discussion

This section discusses opportunities and threats of adopting Wasm and related tools in building IoT systems by relating the observations from the literature to a broader context of IoT software development. As Wasm blurs the difference between IoT service and perception layers, the discussion is separated into broader cloud/edge and device usage contexts. The last section of this chapter discusses the limitations of the literature review work.

5.1 WebAssembly for Cloud/Edge Computing

Wasm emerges as a suitable tool for extending cloud computing capabilities to the network edge and building efficient IoT systems. The primary prerequisites for efficient edge computing systems for IoT, as stated in the background section of this thesis, are decreased overall latency and the capability to migrate computation between nodes effectively. The literature review results align with these requirements, demonstrating the feasibility of using WebAssembly for application offloading between IoT devices and servers. Further supporting this concept, the target platform-independent nature of WebAssembly and the low-latency response capacity of Wasm-based FaaS highlight its robust potential for IoT edge computing systems.

The interoperability of WebAssembly in various applications underpins its potential as an effective tool in the development of cloud and edge computing services. The evidence lies in its integration into existing systems such as Apache OpenWhisk [24] or Docker [25], indicating that building a Wasm-based cloud/edge computing service does not necessitate the development of an entirely new platform. This ability to blend with established technologies suggests a path for future implementations replicating this

interoperability to realize similar successful outcomes. More importantly, this encourages broader adoption of Wasm and bolsters ongoing standardization efforts. Consistent with the views of Kjorveziroski et al. [25], this suggests that developers should be offered the flexibility to select an appropriate runtime system without needing to replace existing solutions. As such, Wasm interoperable systems could become a promising alternative to state-of-the-art cloud computing services.

Broad adoption of Wasm in building IoT systems would require an accessible deployment mechanism for Wasm modules. Radovici et al. [45] called for a design of an executable and shared library file format to define what shared libraries to use and how to link several Wasm modules together. Regarding application migration at the edge, selected literature mentions the feasibility of swarm computing [26] and femtocloud offloading [28] platform, which would require implementing a sophisticated orchestration system. Following the need for an orchestration system, Kjorveziroski et al. [25] describe how the Spin orchestration framework utilizes a component model for dynamically linking Wasm modules and Bindle for defining Wasm bundles with the required dependencies.

Considering these developments, it appears that Wasm modules can be feasibly deployed either on a single host runtime or across a cluster. The intercommunication between modules described for WasmCloud and Spin [25] evidences this possibility. Furthermore, the focus of ThingSpire OS on inter-module communication [32] echoes the same sentiment. Therefore, it is plausible to create a cluster runtime with a front-end that would accept a Wasm bundle with configurations and a back-end leveraging a custom or established orchestration tool like Kubernetes for linking and distributing the Wasm modules. Ideally, this setup should infer the orchestration requirements directly from the application itself, similar to the work from Tiwary et al. [46], where functions are automatically deployed close to the data source, thus reducing manual input and potential error.

5.2 WebAssembly for IoT Devices

The versatility of Wasm allows its modules to function in both user and kernel spaces, as exemplified by various systems. In particular, Wen et al. [30] pointed out that Wasm modules can be executed in the OS kernel space of IoT devices, citing systems like Spin OS, Singularity, and Linux eBPF, which run applications in kernel space. Moreover, another approach has

been proposed by the same group with their construction of WasmAndroid [35]. In this system, they utilize Lua to mediate Wasm system calls before they are processed by the Android kernel. Such developments demonstrate that not only can Wasm runtimes operate across different spaces, but they also have the capacity for integration with other technologies. The potential for blending Wasm with technologies like eBPF and others suggests promising new applications for Wasm in the field of IoT.

The ability to deploy Wasm modules on heterogeneous resource-constraint devices and under various contexts, as opposed to deploying a Wasm bundle on a defined cluster of devices and servers, adds even more complexity to the Wasm ecosystem. With the increasing amount of runtime implementations, it is unclear if the runtimes would support certain Wasm modules. Resource-constraint device runtime would not be capable of providing the vast amount of features that are supported by a more complex system, as it was evident from the implementation of WAIT runtime described in [33]. Thus, it is essential to document the capabilities that are offered by the runtime, most notably through interface standards like WASI. Then, manually or automatically check for the suitability of Wasm modules for a runtime before it gets to be deployed. Otherwise, certain configuration parameters may influence how a Wasm runtime should handle the deployment.

The emergence of various configuration options that describe how Wasm modules must be deployed under certain runtimes potentially creates a bigger issue. Ideally, the configurations should be compatible, leaving the runtimes to interpret the best possible way to deploy the Wasm modules. However, runtimes like Aerogel [38] that are implemented for individual IoT devices rely on a configuration that would be difficult to apply for cluster runtimes. If it is possible for runtimes to ignore the configuration without impacting the functionality of the application, this would not be a big issue. But in a case where configuration defines what temperature sensor should be accessed to make critical decisions, the temperature sensor on a device is likely to be addressed by a bus identifier, while the temperature sensor on a cluster may be addressed by an IP address over a network, both relying on vastly different protocols. Kubernetes ecosystem has been dealing with declarative configuration of deployment across heterogeneous hosts. Thus, it can provide hints on how these issues could be solved for Wasm-based services.

However, it is essential to highlight that a configuration framework poses significant design and implementation challenges. Designing a standard-

ized and flexible configuration system that caters to the needs of different runtimes while preserving the functionality of applications will necessitate a profound understanding of Wasm runtime environments, their characteristics, and their limitations. Moreover, the actual implementation of this system would demand thorough testing and fine-tuning to ensure that it can correctly interpret and adapt configurations across diverse deployment contexts.

5.3 Limitations of the Work

The inclusion and exclusion criteria did not restrict based on research paper type, but it can be argued that some excluded articles could have given similarly valuable information for answering RQ2 and RQ3 while not giving an answer for RQ1. Although the information on the benefits and disadvantages of Wasm for building IoT systems can be synthesized from Wasm research articles that discuss it outside of the IoT context and from research articles that can be found outside of the selected two databases, they are kept outside this thesis's scope due to the limited resources and time for writing the thesis.

6. Conclusion

This thesis is centered on exploring the potential of using WebAssembly within the Internet of Things domain, particularly within the contexts of resource-constrained device usage and cloud/edge computing. The primary focus is understanding how Wasm can be applied to improve or innovate the existing IoT systems, software development practices, and system architectures.

The methodology for this exploration is a state-of-the-art review, where recent and relevant scientific literature and research are analyzed to answer research questions regarding use cases, characteristics, and opportunities of utilizing WebAssembly. This analysis provides insights into the current applications of Wasm in IoT and helps identify gaps and opportunities for further exploration or application.

WebAssembly is applied in various facets of building Internet of Things systems. It is an effective tool for FaaS platforms and application offloading/migration systems, allowing for efficient implementation of cloud and edge computing services. Wasm runtimes can act as a built-in runtime environment in operating systems and facilitate the creation of on-target intermediate representation (IR) compiler toolchains, enabling efficient code execution on resource-constrained devices. Additionally, it is able to function in trusted execution environments. Wasm runtimes also enable hardware resource access control and provide an opportunity for remote debugging to facilitate software development and maintenance processes. With these varied use cases, Wasm demonstrates its capability to integrate with relevant IoT systems.

WebAssembly presents several advantages for Internet of Things systems, most notably its lightweight design that allows it to run efficiently on resource-constrained devices. The flexible interfacing with hardware resources, efficient sandboxing capabilities due to linear memory and

control-flow integrity design, and energy efficiency make it a strong choice. However, there are limitations, such as the potential performance loss, the burden of on-target compiling, and the necessity of extending the interface with the host runtime for certain unsupported features. Moreover, the execution of I/O-intensive computations may be slower due to overhead related to interfacing mechanisms with Wasm. Despite these challenges, Wasm can be seen as a promising technology with substantial potential for shaping how IoT systems are built.

- The study proposes that Wasm could be a viable and efficient tool for extending cloud computing capabilities to the edge network, especially within the IoT domain.
- The ability of Wasm to decrease latency, facilitate computational migration, and its interoperability could improve the efficiency and performance of IoT systems.
- With its platform-independent nature and ability to integrate with established systems, Wasm opens up new possibilities for developing efficient and versatile cloud and edge computing services.
- The findings point towards the possibility of creating a cluster runtime with a front-end that would accept a Wasm bundle with configurations, thus simplifying the deployment process of Wasm modules in IoT systems.
- Ability Wasm to run in both user and kernel spaces presents a technological opportunity, opening new pathways for its applications within the field of IoT.

Future Research Directions

- Addressing the challenges posed by deploying Wasm modules on heterogeneous resource-constraint devices with various configuration requirements.
- Designing a standardized and flexible configuration system around a potential executable and shared library file format that would be suitable

for deploying Wasm modules both on resource-constraint devices and sophisticated clusters.

- Implementing, prototyping, and evaluating orchestration systems in order to assist in designing a configuration system for deploying Wasm bundles.

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